

Training and Development Program Preparation

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Executive Summary

Training and development improve an organization's performance and self-fulfillment by describing the ongoing and formal efforts, by the use of various educational tools and programs (Noe, 2014). These efforts can be applied to professional development and specific job skills. With the incorporation of Consultants who provide a range of expertise that help organizations meet specific needs such as strategy development, training of staff, conduct research projects and others, an organization can create customized training and development curriculums (Mowday, Porter & Steers, 2013). However, before an organization decides to contract a consultant, it has to prepare and monitor its procedures to determine if the investment will pay off. Training and development programs help boost employee motivation and morale, increase process efficiency, increase technology, increase job satisfaction and methods of adopting capacity, increase strategy and product innovation, decrease employee turnover, enhance organizational image and risk management capabilities for instance in sexual harassment and diversity training (Ford, 2014). This white paper looks at the advantages of engaging consultancy services in preparing for or facilitating training and development program.

Introduction

Training and development programs provide an organization's workforce with skills that enable it to handle its duties effectively, thereby improving an organization's effectiveness and delivery (Anitha, 2014). These programs have to be of high quality and affordable. Organizations, therefore, have to carefully consider the purpose for engaging consultants and determine if it is the best way to achieve its goals. A wide range of factors must be considered before selecting a consultant, because success with a consultant starts before the reference check and the first interview (Chambers, 2013). Several important steps have to be followed before

writing a request for proposals. The most crucial are clearly and accurately defining the project, determining the affordability of the consultancy services and restructuring the project in case the costs are too high or splitting the cost with another organization with similar needs and finally selecting the best consultant to solve the problem. The project should have the support of key stakeholders to enhance success chances by ensuring the commitment of members and participants. Consulting costs can be estimated to ensure cost effectiveness by breaking down the project into elements such as consulting fees, equipment, seminars, supplies, in-house staff overtime pay and events and estimating the cost of each.

The high cost of consultancy should not be a deterring factor in hiring them in an organization. Having a problem solved professionally is a cheaper proposition than leaving it unsolved (Jehanzeb & Bashir, 2013). A consultant's fees reflect their level of expertise, experience, and availability of the expertise in the market. Some consultants bill hourly, some on a flat rate, some have their type of fee system, and this should be a subject in selecting a consultant. Cost cutting measures should be employed in case the fees are too high to maintain the quality of the services needed.

Consultants offer substantial help to organizations. These can be in the form of completing tasks within defined periods of time, identify problems and help provide solutions, research new trends, challenges and assess impacts, train staff in essential skills (Ford, 2014). Mediate disputes, assist managements to reach their set goals, develop new business conducting systems, help in recruitment or retention of board members, identify and install new equipment, offer new business perspectives, give an independent perspective for making management decisions, and execute specialized work for some time (Chambers, 2013). By doing this, they address a variety of needs in organizations. This is because they have the relevant skills,

experience, knowledge, and access to information in the areas that consultancy services are required. It is therefore important to engage consultants in the preparing for or to facilitate the development of training and development programs for some reasons after all factors evaluated.

Content Development and Management

Content is imperative in the information economy. It adds value and infiltrates marketing channels and is, therefore, a very powerful tool for the development of a workforce. Getting content noticed and consumed is getting increasingly challenging in a competitive environment flooded with high-value contents. Consultants help create better content for curriculum rejuvenation (Jehanzeb & Bashir, 2013).

Consultants rely on a range of consulting tools in identifying organizational problems and evaluating viable solutions. They assess employee training needs develop and implement training programs, and align training with organizational goals as well as create and manage the budgets for cost effectiveness. They also teach instructors training methodologies, update the programs for training and training material review, supervise the creation and development of training and educational materials, as well as assess training programs and effectiveness of the instructors.

Learning Technology and Options Provision

Organizations are increasingly adopting learning technologies in managing their curriculum and deliver it to employees (Knowles, Holton & Swanson, 2014). They help satisfy the compliance and requirements associated with mandatory training in highly specialized industries. Consultants help select, implement, customize and integrate these technologies to match organizational needs.

Consultants also help an organization compare its employee capabilities with market opportunities. They do this by analyzing a range of possibilities and comparing the capabilities

of the organization with a range of set out options. These options include developing or sourcing new workforce capabilities that will help the organization to expand into new geographical territories and help enter into new market sectors. Consultants highlight and identify changes that are required for the success of the training and development program

Training Agenda and Objective Assessment

Training consultant provides necessary advice on how to structure and organize training and development program and help take full advantage of its efficiency (Jehanzeb & Bashir, 2013). They thoroughly evaluate the functionality and suitability of a training program and plan what is required. This involves prediction and measurement of outcomes and assessing the efficiency of training to ensure full time and the utilization of money. Consultants also determine the need and relevance of training programs and identify the respect in which an organization is lagging. The assessment of the training agenda has to be complete covering every aspect of the lesson materials and instructors' aptitude level.

Since consultants look at client case individually using the expertise in their niche, they can help analyze the employee productivity and bottom line revenues and offer impartial analysis and incorporate this in preparation for and development of training and development programs.

Professional and Experienced Guidance

Consultants are very helpful to an organization as in preparation for an inclusive training by helping an organization to plan, manage and implement a training program (Knowles, Holton & Swanson, 2014). They provide an organization with wisdom gained from their past experiences, and this helps an organization avoid some mistakes concerning cost effectiveness and viability of an employee training program.

When developing a training and development program, it is also important to engage consultants since they offer valuable perspectives that can help an organization when there is no much progress registered from previous and current programs and procedures (Knowles, Holton & Swanson, 2014). Since the consultancy firms are outside parties, they can supply perspectives on organizational dynamics that are difficult to identify or understand from within an institution. These perspectives can then be incorporated in the development of training and development programs.

Mediation of Divergent Opinions

Consultants, in preparation for a training program, can help negotiate opinion differences between board members and staff or volunteers concerning the directions the training and development initiative should take (Bos-Nehles, Riemsdijk & Looise, 2013). This ensures that there is a balance between the needs of all the stakeholders in the development of the program.

Consultants can also help bring up the voices of the voiceless or the ones with less authority in an organization (Noe, 2014). This helps collect valuable opinions that are not often or easily heard by the management or the board members. If this is incorporated in the development of a teaching program, all the stakeholders' needs are taken into consideration, and the effectiveness and viability of the program can be improved in the light of this.

Action Plan and Framework Development

On behalf of the management or the board of directors, consultants can help develop training and development program plan of action (Ford, 2014). This is done after an in-depth look at an organization's risk analysis, cost management, allocations for human resource development and incorporate these in the development of a unique plan of action for the

implementation of the training and development program. It's consulting firm's duty to single out its workforce problems and suggest possible solutions for the development of training modules.

Consultants provide an organization with a framework for effective decision making. They provide organizations with new thinking channels to be incorporated in employee development and guide the process of decision-making and training. Consultants participate in initial meetings with the organization's management team to determine and establish the requirement of the training and development project, prepare a proposal and conduct research, analysis and assessment of scenarios and options (Jehanzeb, Rasheed & Rasheed, 2013). Independent strategy perspectives and recommendations presented in the report help the management in making more informed decisions about employee development.

Focused and Unique Development

Consultants also help organizations define their role; identify their capabilities, strengths, and weaknesses as a basis for the development of training programs. An organization must, therefore, be able to define what it does and incorporate this in the skills of its workforce so that the market can understand its capabilities (Mowday, Porter & Steers, 2013). A consultant examines the product range, employee skills, customer base and marketing communications to determine an organization's current capability.

Consultants also provide the expertise and experience of solving workforce problems. That experience and perspective help management teams to focus on developing strategies that help differentiate an organization from its competitors (Mowday, Porter & Steers, 2013). Consultants also help an organization's management to identify priorities and incorporate these in the development of a training module to realize the strategy.

Work Backlog Reduction

One of the reasons why consultants should be involved in the development or the preparation for training and development is to help free up some time that the managers and directors would use in the development of the course for them to concentrate on other duties (Chambers, 2013). This is important since it eliminates work backlog and saves time thereby guaranteeing professionalism.

Training consultants teach training and development managers and those in charge of employee development. This is one of the most significant areas of a consultant's work. Besides this, a consultant helps in the development of a teaching program for a particular organization. According to Noe (2014), organizations globally spend an average of 54 billion dollars in training alone. An increasing number of business applications require multifaceted IT. Consultant guidance in an organization helps get the training curriculum in tune with skills or teaching new skills in a changing environment or with the employment of new IT systems.

Honesty and Client Priority

Consultants have an honest relationship with their clientele (Jehanzeb, Rasheed & Rasheed, 2013). They, therefore, provide transparent and effective communication in all the training module development phases. They acknowledge organizational weaknesses and limitations and help incorporate this into the development of the training module so that an organization's goals are brought to fruition.

Consultants give contracting firms, top priority status. They fully dedicate themselves to the contracting company's mission, apply high standards, ethically and allocate time reasonably. They perform their work with utmost abilities and resources. In the light of this, they liaise with organizations, heads of departments and executives for the development of training programs that cultivate talents and manage performance (Noe, 2014). Since they are conversant with

market trends in talent management, they are well versed with methodologies in employee training and development models.

Learning Analytics and Provision of Standard, Specialized and Customized Programs

The volume, type, and effectiveness of training module offered by an organization give insights into training and development investment (Cummings & Worley, 2014). This is crucial in the development of an engaging and sustainable workforce. Adding this to the development of training and development programs will help align an organization's workforce with strategic objectives. A consultant helps establish report and analyze valuable learning metrics needed for the preparation of training and development programs.

Every business has its unique needs that it wants to be addressed. It is therefore important for an organization to develop standard leadership development programs. A training and development program can be tailored to fit the needs of an organization (Noe, 2014). Consultants offer specialty programs that take care of specific pain points within an organization to help it prepare for training and development and develop a training module.

Analysis and Reporting

Consultants take an objective look at the organization to identify opportunities for improvement. This is done by studying organizational structure; business processes efficiency assessment and employee and manager interviews. Skill level throughout the organization is also assessed (Bos-Nehles, Riemsdijk & Looise, 2013). The results of these efforts are imperative in preparation for development or choosing a training program. Successful organizations do not, as a development strategy, regulate the size of their workforce. They instead equip their workforce with knowledge and skills to help it conform with to change and dynamic strategies.

Consultant's report outcomes are incorporated training module development, highlighting organizational weaknesses and strengths. Consultants can compare previous encounters with similar works on organizational performance and industry best practices. The recommendations of the reports enable an organization to improve certain aspects of its performance and effectively meet its goals if they are applied in the development of a training module (Knowles, Holton & Swanson, 2014). The findings are reviewed by senior management teams. The consultant then advises the organization on how to best implement recommendations, manage change processes and incorporate them into the training and development in line with the findings. They can also see the need for the employment of technology in the training process and programs to help develop essential skills.

Implementation and Training Delivery

Most consultants complete their involvement in training program development after presenting recommendations and leave the implementation to executives (Anitha, 2014). Some manage the training process, setting schedules and budgeting by acting as project managers for the program. Consultants also help supervise the training process obliterating obstacles that may arise in the implementation process apart from planning and deliver training programs. They also coach executives and key figures for maintenance of momentum of the training and development program (Noe, 2014). Their efforts lead to skills that enable internal staff to act as change champions. Consultants can facilitate effective training in case there is a need for a dynamic trainer to facilitate course internally developed or acquired from an outside provider. Knowledge transfer consultants are skilled at adapting presentations to the nature of training and the audience. Consultants supervise staff training specialists and teach them training methods who in turn deliver them to employees (Noe, 2014). They also direct daily training activities and

evaluate their effectiveness. Some may conduct training courses. Each department identifies its training needs to enhance overall work quality

Organizational Development

Organizations may have important employee development plans but lack resources for their implementation (Cummings & Worley, 2014). They can assist in the achievement of the objectives by offering change and performance management, assessment and analysis and leadership development. Their engagement in the development of training programs is, therefore, crucial.

Bos-Nehles, Riemsdijk and Looise (2013) argue that consultants should not be let to lead and on the process preparing for or developing the training program as this may result in jeopardy of the outcomes of the program. Additionally, consultants must be adaptable and flexible to respond to the individual needs of different organizations. Consultants that are not adaptable do not understand a particular organization's needs and can lead to waste of time and resources in pursuit of irrelevant agenda.

Conclusion

For organizations to stay competitive, they must make their workforce more productive and knowledgeable (Cummings & Worley, 2014). Development opportunity provision helps attract high-quality employees and helps retain those that can assist to contribute to business growth. Consultants and training and development managers help align training and development with organizational goals. They oversee training programs and budgets, organize training programs, create or select course content and materials. Consultants help in ensuring that training methods, content, software, systems and equipment are meaningful and appropriate.

Consultants help an organization achieve its goals by consulting, advising and designing desirable programs as well as coach, guide and train staff. They also develop management and supervisory skills, define organizational missions, goal and objectives as we as assess situations and improve the performance of work. Additionally, they can identify training and operational needs, improve communication within an organization, boost employee motivation and enlarge customer base (Bos-Nehles, Riemsdijk & Looise, 2013).

An effective training program follows systematic steps to meet organizational objectives and participant expectations (Jehanzeb & Bashir, 2013). These include evaluating needs for training, setting an organization's objectives, developing action plans, training initiative implementation and training program evaluation and revising.

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